

**PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS AND PERFORMANCE DIRECTIONS OF
TRADITIONAL THEATER ART****Nurpo'latova Ozoda Hasan qizi,**3rd year student of the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan,
Organization and Management of Culture and Art Institutions

Abstract: In order for the teacher to be sure that the candidate who expressed a desire to study traditional singing was chosen correctly, the child's voice and musical ability, physical development, and correct recommendation for singing were repeatedly checked and interviews were conducted with him. It is appropriate to transfer. The teacher begins to teach singing lessons with the student only after his student has chosen singing and is ready to study it. This article analyzes the specific aspects of selecting a work and training the voice according to the student's voice ability.

Key words: singing, voice selection, voice, range, exercise, trachea, respiratory tract (bronchi), lungs, chest muscles and diaphragm (diaphragm), singing muscle

In order for the performance to be artistically high, it is necessary that the singer's attention, intuition, perception, thinking, imagination, and emotion, and most importantly, the spirit of the voice, take an active part in it. In addition, it should reflect the quality of his personal voice, beautiful and rich timbre, purity of tones (intonation), musical ability and talent, cheerfulness and enthusiasm, outlook, free thinking, character and mentality. In order for the teacher to be sure that the candidate who expressed a desire to study traditional singing is chosen correctly, it is necessary to repeatedly check the child's voice and musical ability, physical development and whether he is recommended for singing, and conduct interviews with him. It is appropriate.

The teacher begins to teach singing lessons with the student only after his student has chosen singing and is ready to study it. He begins the first lessons by entertaining the student by singing bright works that he likes. In particular, the influence of our national anthems on the student's spirit, the mental changes that appear in them, and the ethical-aesthetic development are clearly manifested in the core of teaching in solo performance.

It should be noted that it is much easier to understand a song than a melody. This is because the hymn contains both artistic and musical text. And the melody contains only the musical text, which the student can feel and can even imagine, understand, and perceive during this feeling. But not everyone is lucky enough to express these concepts and ideas in words. In understanding the

chant, the poetic text with its tones helps the student to some extent. Therefore, most students quickly understand the meaning and essence of the song and can express it in words. Perhaps this is the main reason why more young people want to study singing than music. The main goal of training the voice in performing arts is to improve tone mobility and expressiveness. The artist's voice should be clearer, more sonorous, more beautiful, while preserving all the expression of natural speech. Whether it is the stage of the cultural center or the palaces, or in theatrical performances on large squares, whatever the form of performance is, the organizer of these works is the director:

- a) work on the activity of his voice-speech organs and hearing ability;
- b) to thoroughly study the art of speech and the method of working on all sections of stage speech, ultimately, he should be able to guide his performers as well [4, B.43] .

The sum of all the organs involved in the production of sound is called the vocal apparatus. The voice apparatus includes the following organs: oral and nasal cavities and additional cavities that amplify them, larynx, throat and vocal cords, respiratory tract (trachea), air intake channels in the lungs, i.e. include organs such as the airways (bronchi), lungs, chest muscles, and the diaphragm. But that's not all. Nervous systems - motor and sensory nerves in the brain also take an active part in the creation of sound, connecting the centers of the above-mentioned organs. These organs receive efferent communication from the brain through motor nerves. Efferent communication is connected about the state of working organs, that is, information comes through sensory nerves. Organs involved in the production of sound are technical performers focused on a complex process such as sound production, according to the command of the central nervous system. It is impossible to imagine the coordination of the work of the organs of sound production without the participation of the central nervous system. Because both the unification of the functions of these organs and the whole process of singing is a very complex psycho-physiological process that can only be controlled by the central nervous system.

Like the function of all organs, the functioning of the organs of sound production is closely related to each other, as well as to the psychological activity of a person. Without a thorough knowledge of this mechanism, it is difficult to understand the basics of singing, improve it, and prepare a professional singer who can sing well in the future. In reading poetic texts, by practicing the means of raising or lowering the tone of voice, increasing or decreasing the volume, a brighter, more expressive quality is achieved, in contrast to ordinary live spoken speech. Being able to consciously use the voice, to be able to turn it in the right direction at any time, that is, to make the voice elastic, improves the speech [4, B.45]. It is known that the voice originates mainly in the larynx. The larynx is an organ that performs the function of exhalation, protection of the

respiratory tract and lungs, and the production of sound. It consists of a complex structure. The size of the larynx is determined by the thyroid cartilage. Men's larynx is larger than women's larynx. The smallest larynx of men is approximately equal to the largest larynx of women. There are two holes in the larynx, the upper one is connected with the red right passage and the lower one is connected with the pulmonary passage. When a person swallows, the airway is blocked by means of the soft palate and tongue, opening the way to the red esophagus. When a person breathes, the second hole is open. In the process of singing and speaking, this second hole becomes narrower. This situation is important in the creation of a speaker's and singer's voice. As you inhale, the vocal cords become triangular, and this is called a crack. Sound is produced by the convergence and even touching of the vocal folds and the waiting of the vocal folds. The vocal folds are surrounded by internal and external muscles. The second of these muscles is called the singing muscle [4, B.45].

Due to such a structure, the length and thickness of the vocal folds change, as well as the vibration of their individual parts. The richness of sound depends on the vibration of each part of this organ. Another of the mentioned muscles is directly connected with the muscles of the tongue and the lower jaw. These muscles ensure that the larynx goes down and up. As we all know, every object under tension moves the air particles around it when it vibrates, and as a result of these movements, sound waves are created, and these waves reach our ears as sound until they are spread out in space. This is how sound is created in nature. In the human body, the stretched body is the vocal folds. The speaker's voice, the singer's vocal cords when singing, are all created by the harmonic vibrations of the sound layers. As soon as a person wants to sing, all parts of his vocal apparatus are ready to move to achieve this goal, because these organs receive a task signal from the nervous system of the brain.

The process of singing begins when the singer begins to breathe through the mouth and nose. The vocal folds and slits are activated according to signals from the nervous system of the lungs and airways. This situation starts from the moment of exhaling. Adjacent vocal folds block the path of the outgoing air, preventing the breath from escaping freely. Due to the contraction of the air-producing muscles, air begins to affect the vocal folds. Finally, the vocal cords vibrate and produce sound. It is also worth mentioning that even when we sing internally, the vocal cords vibrate, but no sound is produced, because the air has not yet exerted its influence. The sound we hear with our ears is created by the mutual movement of sound layers and air. So, the main core of sound formation is the joint work of the vocal folds and the breath.

The sounds formed in the vocal folds in cooperation with the breath lose most of their power before they pass through the layers of the rest of the surrounding organs and exit, as the resulting sound travels to each layer. it is inevitable that it will vibrate and, therefore, acoustic

changes will occur. That's why these layers are called resonator-resonators of cavities (all members involved in sound production are resonators). These speakers are divided into two. These are the upper and lower vowels. [4, B.47]. The role of music in the education of aesthetic culture is very important. Music, by its very nature, is the foundation of aesthetic culture. The incomparable role of music and literature in social life has been known since ancient times. He accompanies a person from birth to the end of his life in his joyful and anxious days. At the same time, music educates a person, motivates him to do good, teaches him to live a free and prosperous life.

When it comes to the art of Uzbek national singing, its great influence on human feelings and mood depends on how much aesthetic quality is concentrated in a person. It is natural for any person to have musical ability, when music is playing, a person is naturally given to the melody of music, understands it and feels it from the heart. This process is now stronger in music professionals, who have a deep theoretical and practical knowledge of music and an understanding of musical terms. Their musical ability is stronger than that of the music nerds, that is, from the point of view of their professional activities. When they listen to any note, they can understand what pitch it is in or how to analyze it.

The determination of tone, manner, pace and expressiveness, strength, extension, glosses, directions and changes of melody are as original in literature as in music. When thinking about musical ability and the criteria for determining it, teachers should definitely familiarize their students with the history of folk singing, because it is natural that the words of some songs sung in the folk language are unfamiliar or incomprehensible to students. Therefore, it is appropriate for the teacher to explain in the lesson that the song was created on the basis of the origin and simple dialects of the people of that time. At the same time, the student's musical ability is more evident, the student's range of thinking increases.

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